

Supplementary information

Text S1. FET modelling datasets compilation (including **Figures S1-1 to S1-4**)

Text S2. Unification of LC₅₀ values of chemicals in designed mixtures and experimental LC₅₀ values from fish embryo acute toxicity testing (including **Figures S2-1 and S2-2**, and **Table S2-1**)

Table S3. MS2Quant calibrants

Table S4. Designed mixture chemicals (**excel**)

Table S5. Designed mixtures and concentrations (**excel**)

Figure S3. Correlation plot for predicted and theoretical toxic units (**excel**)

Text S1. FET modelling datasets compilation (cleaning and analysis)

The supplementary dataset of the ECHA report contained 2036 entries for Zebrafish embryo LC₅₀ values corresponding to over thousand unique chemicals according identifiers prior to unification.¹⁵ The experimental LC₅₀ values in the dataset were put together from different sources, and were measured under different conditions differing in test length, incubation temperature, exposure solution renewal etc.

In order to clean the dataset, firstly, all chemicals with non-numeric LC₅₀ values were discarded (e.g. when the LC₅₀ value was outside of the tested concentration range, a ">/< concentration" was marked). Additionally, chemicals marked as inorganics were removed as these would not be detectable with LC/HRMS. Additional 3 non-marked inorganic chemicals containing As or Hg were removed, removing in total of 45 entries.

Next, the correctness of provided identifiers was checked based on name, CAS, SMILES, and InChIKey of the chemical entries. All four identifiers were queried for an InChIKey from PubChem using webchem package in R. In case name and SMILES-based InChIKey matched, correct information was assumed, while entries with mis matching InChIKey from name and SMILES notation were checked manually and name-based InChIKey was assumed to be correct. The InChIKey fetched based on SMILES and name agreed for 1444 and disagreed for 92 entries. For 455 entries the fetched information was missing for either name or SMILES notation.

Mismatching and missing information entries were manually checked. In total 1283 entries were deemed to have sufficient metadata for further data analysis. These chemicals were standardized for LC amenability (e.g. removing salts and chirality). In total, 782 unique chemicals with numeric LC₅₀ values were left in the dataset after standardization of identifiers.

Next, chemicals selected for experimental validation (23) were removed from the dataset, leaving 759 unique chemicals in the dataset.

In order to train a model to predict FET LC₅₀, the experimental conditions for LC₅₀ determination were categorized and analyzed. Here, we considered the length of the test, incubation temperature, exposure solution renewal approach, and if the embryos were dechorionated prior to toxicity testing. Also, LC₅₀ values were unified, that is if the LC₅₀ value measured under exact same conditions (incubation temperature, length of the test, dechorionation, exposure solution renewal) and the LC₅₀ values differed more than 0.5 log-mM, then the chemical was removed from the dataset, otherwise, the LC₅₀ values were averaged. In total, 7 chemicals were removed due to non-agreeing LC₅₀ values resulting in 752 chemicals.

Figure S1-1. The frequency of categorical values in the cleaned FET dataset (752 chemicals)

Only a small fraction of the experimental data was measured under sufficiently similar conditions to the OECD TG 236 - 47 chemicals corresponded to the 96h measurements with 26 °C and without dechorionation. Using category-based filtering, the largest dataset with 410 unique chemicals would correspond to 120h, 28 °C, static mode and dechorionated embryos. Thus, we decided to test the following datasets for modelling:

- 1) "FET dataset" – 96h, 26 °C, static, not dechorionated (209)
- 2) "FET+MS2Tox dataset" + MS2Tox AFT (977) "

Since the static mode measurements were dominating in the dataset, we included measurements with static mode only in .

For "FET dataset", the aim was to include all data measured under similar experimental conditions to the OECD TG 236, that is 96h test, incubation temperature of 26 °C, static mode data without dechorionation. To increase the number of chemicals in the dataset, we included all data with test length of 48, 72, and 96h, incubated at either 26 °C or 28 °C, and used robust linear regression to transfer all existing data to the same scale with the TG 236 requirements.

Reasonable correlation was seen between datapoints measured under same temperature, even though the number of common datapoints was generally low. First, 48h and 72h measurements were transferred to the 96h LC₅₀ scale for both 26 °C (Figure SI-2A) and 28 °C (Figure SI-2B) independently. The two datasets had 13 chemicals in common that had a Pearson's R^2 of 0.97, thus, the data measured under 28 °C was transferred to the same scale with data measured under 26 °C (Figure SI-2C). This resulted in 209 chemicals suitable for modelling.

Figure SI-2. After filtering data to only include static mode and not dechlorinated measurements the data was transferred to OECD TG 236 experimental conditions. A) The LC₅₀ correlation between 48h and 72h long measurements with 96h at 26 °C (5 and 6 chemicals, Pearson's R^2 of 1 and 0.99), B) The LC₅₀ correlation between 48h and 72h long measurements with 96h at 28 °C available (36 and 42 chemicals, Pearson's R^2 of 0.94 and 0.92), and C) LC₅₀ correlation between all chemicals transferred to 26 °C scale compared to 28 °C scale (13 chemicals, Pearson's R^2 of 0.97) used to transfer all LC₅₀ values to 26 °C scale.

For "FET+MS2Tox dataset", the aim was to expand the training data of "FET dataset" by joining adult fish toxicity data with FET data. For this, the training data of MS2Tox was used as basis. We used the three adult fish species – fathead minnow, bluegill, rainbow trout – where we first removed the chemicals used in the designed mixtures, and checked for correlation with the "FET dataset". Over all three fish, 51 unique chemicals were common with the "FET dataset". For each species separately, the number of unique common chemicals were 37, 36, and 35 (65, 63, and 71 of total common entries), and the Pearson's R^2 were 0.82, 0.84, and 0.79, for bluegill, fathead minnow, and rainbow trout, respectively (Figure SI-3). Fathead minnow was best correlated with the FET dataset and was chosen as the basis for data transfer to FET LC₅₀ scale.

Figure SI-3. The correlation plots between FET LC₅₀ and AFT LC₅₀ for bluegill, fathead minnow, and rainbow trout respectively.

The AFT data was transferred to fathead minnow scale, the number of common datapoints was 186 and 156 including 179 and 149 unique chemicals with the correlation (Pearson's R^2) of 0.93 and 0.91 for bluegill and rainbow trout, respectively (Figure SI-4A). Using all common chemicals between the joined three adult fish species and FET dataset, that is 199 datapoints including 51 unique chemicals, the AFT data was joined with the FET dataset (Pearson's R^2 of 0.83, Figure SI-4B) resulting "FET+MS2Tox dataset" with 977 unique chemicals.

Figure SI-4. A) Correlation between LC₅₀ values for fathead minnow vs bluegill and rainbow trout. B) correlation between LC₅₀ values of all unified AFT vs FET.

Text S2. Unification of LC₅₀ values for the chemicals in designed mixtures

In order to bring all LC₅₀ values to the same experimental condition scale with the training data (corresponding to OECD TG 236), we first aimed to use correlations between different experimental conditions within the cleaned FET dataset.

For four chemicals (isoniazid, chloramphenicol, nicotine, aconitine) the correlation between data measured under 26 °C and 28 °C from data unification was used (Figure SI-2C).

For three chemicals (caffeine, doramectin, acetyl salicylic acid) the correlation between test length of 120h and 96h (unified dataset over 48h, 72h and 96h from data unification) was used.

For three chemicals (metolachlor, 2-naphthalenol, acetochlor), the correlation between AFT and FET data (Figure SI-4B) was used for transferring data to FET scale. For metholachlor and

2-naphthalenol, LC₅₀ from fathead minnow was available and used, while for acetochlor, LC₅₀ values from bluegill and rainbow trout were used first to transfer the LC₅₀ to fathead minnow scale using the correlations from Figure S1-4A, followed by transferring the LC₅₀ to FET LC₅₀ scale, and the LC₅₀ values were averaged.

For eight chemicals, the FET LC₅₀ was determined experimentally and used as ground truth (Figure S2-1). For three chemicals, the LC₅₀ values could not be transferred to the OECD TG 236 experimental conditions scale, and these chemicals were not used in statistical analysis. All unifications are visualized on Figure S2-2 and summarized in Table S2-1.

Figure S2-1. Concentration-response curves for eight chemicals for which FET LC₅₀ values were determined experimentally.

Table S2-1. The unification approaches used for the chemicals in designed mixtures.

name	Original LC ₅₀ (different experimental conditions)	LC ₅₀ unified from FET data	LC ₅₀ unified from AFT data	LC ₅₀ experimental	FET LC ₅₀ final logmM	Tox value category	LC ₅₀ unification model (with FET dataset)	N (unique)	R ²	p
Cyanazine	-0.50	-0.50	-1.02	NA	-0.50	1	ready			
Triclosan	-2.84	-2.62	-3.04	-2.96	-2.96	1	experimental (OECD TG236)			
Isoniazid	0.98	0.70	NA	NA	0.70	1	temp28C_length96h_static	13	0.97	5.51E-08
Chloramphenicol	0.21	0.03	NA	NA	0.03	1	temp28C_length96h_static	13	0.97	5.51E-08
Nicotine	-0.66	-0.72	NA	NA	-0.72	1	temp28C_length96h_static	13	0.97	5.51E-08
Aconitine	-1.30	-1.28	NA	NA	-1.28	1	temp28C_length96h_static	13	0.97	5.51E-08
Caffeine	0.17	-0.02	NA	NA	-0.02	1	temp26C_length120h_static	19	0.84	8.58E-06
Febantel	-3.12	-2.84	NA	-2.63	-2.63	1	experimental (OECD TG236)			
Doramectin	-3.19	-2.90	NA	NA	-2.90	1	temp26C_length120h_static	19	0.84	8.58E-06
Acetyl salicylic acid	-0.57	-0.66	NA	NA	-0.66	1	temp26C_length120h_static	19	0.84	8.58E-06
Perflurodecanoic acid (PFDA)	-1.79	NA	NA	NA	-1.79	2	could not unify			
Malathion	-1.86	-2.14	-1.28	-1.97	-1.97	1	experimental (OECD TG236)			
Triclocarban	-4.08	NA	-3.55	-3.29	-3.29	1	experimental (OECD TG236)			
Benzhydrazide	-0.29	-0.29	NA	NA	-0.29	1	ready (information on xposure solution renewal missing)			
Metolachlor	-1.34	NA	-1.46	NA	-1.46	1	AFT_allfish_fatheadminnowscale_FET_correlation	51	0.83	6.02E-52
Acetochlor	-1.57	NA	-2.20	NA	-2.20	1	(only values for bluegill and rainbow trout, both to fathead minnow scale; later LC50 averaged) AFT_allfish_fatheadminnowscale_FET_correlation	51	0.83	6.02E-52
Fluazinam	-2.99	NA	NA	-3.55	-3.55	1	experimental (OECD TG236)			
Genistein	-1.69	NA	NA	-1.90	-1.90	1	experimental (OECD TG236)			
2-Naphthalenol	-1.60	NA	-1.55	NA	-1.55	1	AFT_allfish_fatheadminnowscale_FET_correlation	51	0.83	6.02E-52
Benodanil	-1.69	NA	NA	NA	-1.69	2	could not unify			
N-Phenyl-14-benzenediamine	-1.69	NA	NA	NA	-1.69	2	could not unify			
Octhlinone	-2.94	NA	-3.18	-3.16	-3.16	1	experimental (OECD TG236)			
Dinoseb	-3.44	NA	-3.33	-3.61	-3.61	1	experimental (OECD TG236)			

Figure S2-2 The comparison for all derived FET LC₅₀ values for designed mixtures chemicals.

Figure S3. The squared Spearman correlation coefficients for toxic units predicted in positive (light blue) and negative (dark blue) ESI mode based on A) SMILES, B) mixture-specific MS², and C) merged MS² spectra. The TUs corresponding to chemical with unified LC₅₀ values are marked with circles, and TUs for chemicals with non-unified LC₅₀ values are marked with crosses. Only the chemicals with unified LC₅₀ values were used in correlation analysis.